

A COMPARITIVE STUDY IN EMPLOYEE GRIEVANCE AND ITS IMPACT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

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Abstract: Every discomfort or dissatisfaction an employee feels or even imagines in a company is seen as a grievance if it is not properly addressed. When they initially join the company, every person has distinct expectations for the company. If these expectations are not met over time, there will ultimately be unhappiness, and if that unhappiness is not properly addressed, it will eventually take the form of a complaint.

Anger is an upward communication. It gives managers essential early information about anticipated problems. Anger can be real or imagined, justified or not, and truthful or false. A business cannot exist without complaints.

Keywords: Grievance, Performance, Redressal procedure, Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Each workplace occasionally has disagreements, and how these disagreements are resolved is essential to maintaining a productive and healthy work environment. How well problems are addressed will determine how effective grievance management is and solved. It is very significant in today's environment. Instead of "human resources," firms today frequently refer to their most important assets as "human capital." Therefore, it is necessary to confirm the accuracy of these assertions (Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences). Monitoring how soon employee problems are addressed and remedied can help with this.

Employee complaints can be triggered by a variety of factors, including promotions, employment requirements and conditions, pay and benefits, safety and health at work, performance assessments, and how a supervisor and other employees treat an employee (Ibrahim Rihan, 1998). Employee complaints may be brought about by a variety of factors, including inadequate feedback, lack of recognition, unclear performance requirements, unfair standards, being screamed at or blamed, violating commitments, and being overworked or stressed out (Randolph and Blanchard, 2007:134).

Instead than focusing on confrontation among all employees, industrial conflict now concentrates on problems between employers and employees (B. Walker and R. Hamilton, 2011). A number of international research on particular employee-employer issues are included in this narrative overview. The literature review has four primary phases, which are as follows:

- The frequency of incidences giving rise to a grievance;
- The employee's response to a potential grievance issue;
- The effectiveness of the grievance processing; and
- The outcomes.

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A crucial element of effective grievance management is the ability of managers and supervisors to recognize, analyze, and resolve the underlying causes of potential employee displeasure before they manifest as official complaints (Chaykowski & Slotsve, 1992). (Ivancevich 2001) contends that supervisors should take each complaints seriously, consult with the union representative to gather all pertinent data, and then then, after carefully weighing all the available facts, address the employee who has raised the issue. Once the dispute has been settled amicably, management must move on to other issues.

II. LITERARY REVIEW

The American Civil Liberties Union defines a grievance as "any displeasure or dissatisfaction, whether stated or not, whether justified or not, arising out of anything linked with the firm that an employee thinks, believes, or even feels to be unfair, unjust, or inequitable." Employee satisfaction measures how content and satisfied employees are at work and how well their needs and wants are being met. Employee happiness is a factor in inspiring workers, assisting them in reaching their goals, and promoting a positive work environment, according to a number of assessments.

Today, a company's ability to address the growing issues of employee dissatisfaction and maintain staff happiness determines its productivity and success.

When handling employee complaints, many management theories are applied. Supervisors that use an integrative approach prioritize both themselves and the aggrieved employees. Transparency, information exchange, and the examination of disparities are its main focuses. Compromise requires a healthy amount of care for both oneself and others. The concept of giving and receiving is the foundation of this.

Combining efforts when doing so will benefit both parties. In the controlling style of monitoring, there is a considerable worry for oneself and little concern for the person who has been harmed. The supervisor in this situation is power-obsessed and competitive while also being in a losing situation. The personalities of managers have an impact on how complaints are handled as well (Zulkiflee Bin Daud).

Extroverts (people who are outgoing, sociable, and assertive), agreeable (managers who are kindhearted, inclined to agree with subordinates, and concerned with finding solutions that are acceptable to all parties), and conscientious managers (those who are task-oriented, accountable, information-seeking, and believe in facts rather than emotions) are a few examples of the different types of managers.

An empirical study conducted in Malaysia found that extraversion has a significant negative impact on integrating style. A dominant style is significantly influenced by consciousness, while a compromise style is significantly influenced by emotional stability.

(Ben Letham, 2007) asserts that an organization's environmental design significantly affects both job satisfaction and workers' high levels of job involvement. In an organization with a good environmental design, conflicts and ambiguity are simpler to settle. The author even claims that in order to reduce employee discontent, management must provide a setting in which working patterns are clearly reflected in the tasks.

According to (Ingram, 1992), factors that contribute to job satisfaction include the work itself, coworkers, promotions, pay, and supervision in connection to customer orientation. Progression has a significant impact on job satisfaction. It is the manager's obligation to monitor and improve employee satisfaction levels related to supervision quality, working circumstances, intrinsic compensation and benefits, and corporate policies in order to help the employees attain the necessary level of pleasure.

The research cited above makes it very evident that in the present cutthroat corporate environment, employee satisfaction and complaints should be given top importance. In order to address employee complaints, every business should work to establish a grievance system that is clear-cut, accessible, and fast.

This is essential to any organization's success. But the most important factor in this process is everyone's commitment. If employers want the grievance process to be successful, all employees, but especially supervisors, should act as role models. This further suggests that there should be a solid communication system in place and that all employees should routinely get training on the grievance procedure.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- PRIMARY OBJECTIVE
 - To identify and examine the root causes of employee complaints and how they affect job satisfaction.
- SECONDARY OBJECTIVE
 - To understand the company's complaint handling procedures;
 - To understand the company's complaint handling procedures;
 - To pinpoint the primary sources of discontent;
 - To gauge the level of employee happiness across numerous measures;
 - To comprehend the connection between employee complaints and satisfaction.

The research technique is the process used to collect information and data in order to make business decisions. The method could include published research, interviews, surveys, and data from the past as well as current data. A survey and questionnaire are used to acquire the data for this investigation.

"A grievance is a written accusation of unfair treatment made by an employee." (Dale Yoder, 1958)

FORMS OF GRIEVANCE

Fig 1: FORMS OF GRIEVANCE

- FACTUAL GRIEVANCE

A factual complaint is made when the employees' sincere expectations are not satisfied.
- IMAGINARY GRIEVANCE

It takes root in an employee's head not as a result of any issues at work but rather as a result of misinformation or distorted impressions of the workplace.
- DISGUISED GRIEVANCE

Grievances might be a result of events that are out of their control. These motivations typically originate from sources outside of the workplace, such as family, friends, or any other group.

CAUSES OF GRIEVANCE

GRIEVANCE

Fig 2: CAUSES OF GRIEVANCE

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- WORK ENVIRONMENT

Unfair restrictions, malfunctioning devices or systems, inferior supplies, unfavorable working conditions, and lack of recognition.

- SUPERVISION

Prejudice, favoritism, loyalty to castes, nepotism, and regional feelings are perceived as such.

- WORK GROUP

Incompatibility with peers and a feeling of being neglected.

- WORK ORGANIZATION

Rigid, strict rules and lack of recognition.

GRIEVANCE PROCEDURE

Grievance procedures allow you to file a complaint and lead it through many stages until it is resolved.

The following components should be present in a grievance procedure:

1. Adherence to existing legislation - The procedures should be developed to satisfy existing legal obligations. Any equipment that may have previously been provided by the legislation may be used by the procedure when suitable.
2. Acceptability – Everyone must agree that the grievance process is fair. In order to be widely recognized, it must provide (a) a spirit of fair play and fairness to the worker, (b) management exerting authority in a reasonable manner, and (c) an adequate degree of union membership.
3. Training - To guarantee the smooth operation of the grievance system, supervisors and union representatives must receive training in grievance handling.
4. Follow-up - The personnel department should regularly assess how the method is doing and implement any necessary structural improvements in order to increase its effectiveness.
5. Simplicity - The approach should be simple enough for every employee to grasp. It is best to take as few steps as possible. Establishing effective grievance channels is crucial. Employees must know who to approach at various levels of authority. It is possible to effectively communicate information about the process to all staff using pictures, charts, diagrams, etc.
6. Promptness - Effective human management depends on complaints being handled quickly. Justice is denied when it is delayed. The procedure requires a prompt resolution of the problem. The following components may be added to the approach to make it accomplish this:

- (1) Wherever feasible, grievances should be settled at the lowest level;
- (2) Usually, no subject should be discussed more than twice;
- (3) A variety of grievances may be brought to the attention of the appropriate authorities;
- (4) Deadlines ought to be established at each stage and strictly followed at every level; and
- (5) It might be useful to separate out grievances into those resulting from personnel relationships and others arising out of employment circumstances.

An efficient grievance procedure handles problems as they arise. A successful grievance procedure anticipates them and thwarts them at the pass.

ESSENTIAL INGREDIENTS OF GRIEVANCE PROCEDURE

“It's not always obvious who is right and who is wrong. But what is right and wrong never changes.”

(Prof. M. S. Rao, 2019)

The grievance process must be clear-cut and straightforward. It ought to be well stated. It must abide by the law as it is now without exception. Delaying the grievance process might lead to a catastrophe, thus it should not be done. Regular training is necessary for the seniors and supervisors participating in this process to be able to manage it effectively. Follow-up is necessary to monitor the status of the complaint and routinely improve the procedures.

An important focus of the 15th session of the Indian Labor Conference, held in 1957, was the requirement for a national grievance system that would be acceptable to both management and unions.

IMPACT OF GRIEVANCE

Employee morale is severely affected when a conflict arises, which has an adverse effect on how they perform. Having a complaint has a detrimental effect on performance, even for high achievers.

The following is a list of some negative effects of complaints:

- Loss of motivation at work;
- A lack of commitment and morale;
- Poor performance;
- An increase in costs and waste;
- Staff turnover, and
- Insubordination, are all possible consequences.

GRIEVANCE REDRESSAL PROCEDURE

The grievance redressal procedure's objective is to provide an easily accessible method for grievance resolution in order to increase employee satisfaction and, as a result, increase the productivity and efficiency of the business.

- Concerning a grievance, the departmental representative, who is a representative of management, should be approached. He must provide an answer within 48 hours.
- The department head must reply to the dissatisfied employee's complaint within three days if the departmental representative is unable to remedy the problem.
- If the offended employee disagrees with the department head's choice, they may take the matter to the grievance committee.
- The grievance committee delivers a report to management with suggestions within seven days. The management has three days to notify the aggrieved employee of its decision after obtaining the grievance committee's findings. The employee may request a revision if he disagrees with the final judgment. Management shall notify the employee of its decision within seven days.
- Requests for voluntary arbitration may be made if the complaint has not yet been addressed.

REDRESSAL PROCEDURE

Fig 3: COMMON REDRESSAL PROCEDURE

Fig 4: STEP LADDER PROCEDURE

BENEFITS OF HAVING A GRIEVANCE PROCEDURE

It is important to provide employees an opportunity to express their dissatisfaction, and a grievance system may ensure that their concerns are handled seriously. Written grievance policies may demonstrate an organization's regard for the individual while also outlining its fair dispute resolution process.

- It encourages employees to raise concerns without fear of consequences.
- It provides a swift and equitable means of resolving issues.
- It prevents less important disagreements from developing into bigger ones.
- It gives the staff a way to express their annoyances and discontent.
- It contributes to fostering a culture of openness and trust at work.
- As work-related issues are resolved, the employer is spared time and money.

EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION

The majority of employees need motivation in order to feel good about their work and provide their best effort. Some workers are motivated financially, while others are emotionally moved by accolades and rewards. Employee productivity is strongly impacted by their level of motivation at work. Higher output rates are the outcome of motivated and passionate workers performing their tasks to the best of their ability.

A significant problem for managers and leaders for a long time has been the inability to inspire their staff. Lackluster workers are more likely to put in little to no effort, avoid coming into the office as much as possible, quit the firm if given the option, and deliver mediocre work.

On the other hand, motivated workers are more likely to be persistent, creative, and productive, generating high-quality work that they choose to take on. Many scholars have studied motivation extensively. Employers must get to know their employees well in order to support each one of them specifically based on their particular needs and aspirations.

In this article, we want to underline the importance of motivation in the workplace in order to improve worker performance and productivity. However, we would want to talk about the theories and methods of workplace motivation. Motivation is

a result of the interaction of conscious and unconscious factors, including the degree of need or want, the incentive or reward value of the goal, and the expectations of the individual and his or her peers.

These components act as defenses for one's actions. As an illustration, consider a student who spends more time studying for a test to earn a higher grade. Both internal and external cues can pique a person's interest and drive to devote themselves to a task, line of work, or subject, or to make an effort to accomplish a goal.

“Employee satisfaction is defined as a collection of positive or negative sentiments that employees have about their employment.”

(Keith Davis, 1985)

FACTORS INFLUENCING EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION

Employee satisfaction ensures that people are happy with their jobs and eager to give the organization their all. Such people seldom ever think about advancing their careers or motivating others to work hard for the sake of the firm.

- The working conditions at a firm have a big impact on how happy employees are; these workers are the most unsatisfied and unhappy with their employment since they lack a comfortable workspace.
- The second most important factor determining employee happiness is employee benefits. According to their position, responsibilities, and obligations within the organization, employees must get suitable compensation. An underpaid employee will quickly generate problems for the entire business. Make sure that monetary incentives and prizes are directly proportional to the amount of effort an individual puts out.
- The availability of training and development programs as well as possibilities for career growth is a crucial factor that influences employee happiness.
- Corporate laws and regulations, as well as employment practices, have a big impact on employee happiness.
- Relationships with coworkers, managers, and supervisors are crucial in today's workplaces. Businesses with a better chance of success are those who can maintain these connections in balance.
- Given the changing nature of the business world, those who are happy and content may lack the drive to seek out methods to better things or change direction. They may also not be top performers. In the present political climate, this is frequently a bad viewpoint to have. Instead, a company needs workers that are passionate, motivated, and open to trying new things.

Fig 5: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF EMPLOYEE GRIEVANCE AND SATISFACTION

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IV. CONCLUSION

The aforementioned conversations demonstrate that in the present cutthroat corporate environment, employee contentment and complaints should both be given high consideration. In order to address employee complaints, every business should work to establish a grievance system that is clear-cut, accessible, and fast. This is essential to any organization's success.

Every sadness or dissatisfaction an employee feels or even imagines in a company is seen as a grievance if it is not properly addressed. When they initially join the company, every person has distinct expectations for the company. If these expectations are not met over time, there will ultimately be unhappiness, and if that unhappiness is not properly addressed, it will eventually take the form of a complaint. A business cannot exist without complaints.

Due to the unfavorable relationship between employee complaints and job happiness, every organization should make an effort to reduce employee complaints and hence raise employee satisfaction.

But the most important factor in this process is everyone's commitment. If employers want the grievance process to be successful, all employees, but especially supervisors, should act as role models. This further suggests that there should be a solid communication system in place and that all employees should routinely get training on the grievance procedure.

The association between the common causes of complaints in the hotel industry and employee satisfaction on several work-related measures is thoroughly understood thanks to this study.

To increase employee happiness, the company must focus on reducing employee complaints. It follows that the two topics that should be given significant priority are employee satisfaction and employee grievance. An efficient grievance procedure handles problems as they arise. A successful grievance procedure anticipates them and thwarts them at the pass.

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